

A STUDY ON AWARENESS AND EFFECTIVE UTILIZATION OF ESI BENEFITS

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ABSTRACT

Employee State Insurance (ESI) Scheme is a huge social security. It is different from other types of insurance. It supports comprehensive full medical care and reasonable economic assistance to the beneficiaries in contingencies like hazards of sickness, maternity, disablement and death due to employment injury. It is one of the most effective and continual social measures available to the employees in working environment. The purpose of the study is to analysis the awareness and satisfaction with the level of Utilization of ESI policy. A questionnaire was framed and given to find awareness and effects of utilization of ESI policy. Simple random sampling method has used in the research. The data collected has been analyzed through various statistical tools like Chi-square and Correlation. The degree of awareness of such benefits depends upon the age, gender, education, occupation and years of service of the employees.

INTRODUCTION

The ESI Act 1948 covers certain health-related events that the workers are usually

exposed to. These include sickness, temporary or permanent disability, maternity, etc. The Act also encompasses the occurrence of occupational diseases or death due to employment injury leading to loss in wages or earning capacity, either totally or partially. The scheme is jointly is administrated by the central and state governments. This scheme provides socio-economic protection to worker population and dependents covered under the scheme. ESI is a self –financing social security and health insurance scheme for Indian workers. For all employees earning ₹25,000 or less per month as wages, the employer employees contribute 1.75% of their wages and the employers contribute 4.75% of the wages of eligible beneficiaries/employees towards premium payments employee with effective from 1.1.97. The ESI Act aims at upholding the human dignity during crises through protection from deprivation, destitution, and social degradation by way of empowering the society the retention of socially useful and productive manpower.

OBJECTIVES

To understand the level of awareness towards Employee State Insurance (ESI) policy. To analyze the satisfaction and problem of employees towards ESI schemes. To examine the level of utilization of ESI benefits and services among employees.

NEED

To view the level of maturity towards the employee state insurance (ESI) policy. To study on the concern benefits utilized by the employee in organization. The preference given within the organization rules & regulations.

SCOPE

The study also focus on satisfaction level of employees towards the ESI benefits. The study aims to analyze employees' awareness towards schemes and its benefits. To understand the ESI policy in the organization.

LIMITATIONS

The awareness level differs from employee to employee. Collecting response among number of employees are little difficult. Time constraints.

LITERATURE SURVEY

C. A Parri And D Ranjithkumar (2016)

A Study On Employees Problems In Utilizing Esi Benefits As A Special Reference To Erode District Of Tamil

Nadu. In The Study Main Focus Were Given The Problems In Utilization Of Esi Benefits And Awareness Of Benefits. The employees are aware about the ESI benefits but they don't utilize the benefits in a effective way. **Mayer. Brown (2013)** "Asia Employment Law" quarterly review 2013 Employee State Insurance revised ESI inspection guidelines, prosecution and survey and complaints updated on 1st April 2012 and in 7th May 2012 disabled employees and dependents: ESI claims procedures also updated as published in the said journal. **Sumner (2011)** focused a study on information sharing among health care employers using technology. The study was to determine the benefits, risks and past experiences of those involved in information sharing. The study presented that human resource professionals can utilize technology and existing theory to properly implement information sharing techniques into their organizations.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH DESIGN

A research design is a framework that has been created to find answers to research questions. **TYPES OF RESEARCH**

DESCRIPTIVE RESEARCH

Descriptive research aims to accurately and systematically describe a population, situation, or phenomenon.

SAMPLING METHOD

The sampling technique used in this study is simple random sampling

TARGET RESPONDENT

The sample size of the present study is 121 respondents from Chennai.

DATA FOR STUDY

The study depends on both primary as well as secondary data.

DATA PROCESSING

PRIMARY DATA The primary data has been collected from the employees of the organization. **SECONDARY DATA** The secondary data has been collected from journals, magazines websites, and annual reports.

TOOL FOR ANALYSIS

PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS

It refers to a special kind of rate, percentages are used in making comparisons between two or more series of data. A percentage is used to determine the relationship between the series.

CHI-SQUARE

A chi-square test is a statistical test used to compare observed results with expected results.

CORRELATION

A correlational research design investigates relationships between variables without the researcher controlling or manipulating any of them. It reflects the strength and/or direction

of the relationship between two (or more) variables.

PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS

1. PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS FOR GENDER OF THE RESPONDENT

valid	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
male	61	50.4	50.4	50.4
female	60	49.6	49.6	100.0
Total	121	100.0	100.0	

INFERENCE

From the above table it is found that out of 121 respondents, 50.41% are male and 49.51% are female

2. PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS FOR AGE OF THE RESPONDENT

valid	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative Percent
21 - 30	40	33.1	33.1	33.1
31 - 40	40	33.1	33.1	66.1
41 - 50	31	25.6	25.6	91.7

Abv 51	10	8.3	8.3	100.0
Total	121	100.0	100.0	

INFERENCE

3. PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS FOR EDUCATION OF THE RESPONDENT

valid	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
SSLC	20	16.5	16.5	16.5
HSC	50	41.3	41.3	57.9
ITI / Diploma	10	8.3	8.3	66.1
Graduate	31	25.6	25.6	91.7
others	10	8.3	8.3	100.0
Total	121	100.0	100.0	

INFERENCE

From the above table it is found that out of 121 respondents, 17% are SSLC, 41% are

HSC, 8% are ITI / Diploma, 26% are Graduate and 8% are other.

4. PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS FOR INCOME OF THE RESPONDENT

valid	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
less than 10000	30	24.8	24.8	24.8
10001 – 15000	31	25.6	25.6	50.4
15001 – 20000	30	24.8	24.8	75.2
20001 – 25000	30	24.8	24.8	100.0
Total	121	100.0	100.0	

INFERENCE

From the above table it is found that out of 121 respondents, 25% are less than 10000, 26% are 10001 – 15000, 25% are 15001 – 20000, 25% are 20001 – 25000.

5. PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS AWARENESS ABOUT THE

BENEFITS FOR OF THE RESPONDENT

valid	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative Percent
fully aware	40	33.1	33.1	33.1
partially aware	50	41.3	41.3	74.4
not at all aware	31	25.6	25.6	100.0
Total	121	100.0	100.0	

INFERENCE

From the above table it is found that out of 121 respondents, 33% are fully aware, 41% are partially aware and 26% are not at all aware

6. PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS FOR FREQUENTLY UTILIZING BENEFITS OF THE RESPONDENT

valid	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative Percent
always	40	33.1	33.1	33.1
often	20	16.5	16.5	49.6
sometimes	20	16.5	16.5	66.1
rarely	20	16.5	16.5	82.6
never	21	17.4	17.4	100.0
Total	121	100.0	100.0	

INFERENCE

From the above table it is found that out of 121 respondents, 33% are always, 17% are often, 17% are sometimes, 17% are rarely and 17% are never.

7. PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS FOR SERVICE/FACILITY PROVIDED BY ESI OF THE RESPONDENT

valid	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
extremely unlikely	60	49.6	49.6	49.6
unlikely	20	16.5	16.5	66.1
average	20	16.5	16.5	82.6
likely	11	9.1	9.1	91.7
extremely likely	10	8.3	8.3	100.0
Total	121	100.0	100.0	

INFERENCE

From the above table it is found that out of 121 respondents, 50% are extremely unlikely, 17% are unlikely, 17% are average, 9% are likely and 8% are extremely likely.

8. PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS FOR OPINION ABOUT THE PROCEDURE OF THE RESPONDENT

valid	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative Percent
complex	51	42.1	42.1	42.1
simple	30	24.8	24.8	66.9
no opinion	40	33.1	33.1	100.0
Total	121	100.0	100.0	

INFERENCE

From the above table it is found that out of 121 respondents, 42.15% are complex, 24.79% are simple and 33.06% are no opinion.

9. PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS FOR PROBLEMS FACED BY THE INSURED PERSON OF THE RESPONDENT

valid	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
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distance to the esi dispensary	20	16.5	16.5	16.5
lack of the medicines and other facilities	40	33.1	33.1	49.6
Bottleneck procedures	31	25.6	25.6	75.2
delay in getting of claims	10	8.3	8.3	83.5
misbehaviour or restrictions of supporting staff	20	16.5	16.5	100.0
Total	121	100.0	100.0	

INFERENCE

From the above table it is found that out of 121 respondents, 16.53% are distance to the esi dispensary, 33.06% are lack of medicines and other facilities, 25.82% are bottleneck procedures, 8.26% are delay in getting claims and 16.53% are misbehaviour or restrictions of supporting staff.

10. PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS FOR ESI INFLUENCE EMPLOYEE RETENTION ENGAGEMENT OF THE RESPONDENT

valid	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly disagree	20	16.5	16.5	16.5
disagree	50	41.3	41.3	57.9
neutral	20	16.5	16.5	74.4
agree	21	17.4	17.4	91.7
strongly agree	10	8.3	8.3	100.0
Total	121	100.0	100.0	

INFERENCE

From the above table it is found that out of 121 respondents, 17% are strongly disagree, 41% are disagree, 17% are neutral, 17% are agree and 8% are strongly agree.

11. PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS FOR OVERALL OPINION ABOUT ESI BENEFITS OF THE RESPONDENT

valid	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
very good	30	24.8	24.8	24.8
good	30	24.8	24.8	49.6
average	20	16.5	16.5	66.1
bad	20	16.5	16.5	82.6
very bad	21	17.4	17.4	100.0
Total	121	100.0	100.0	

INFERENCE

From the above table it is found that out of 121 respondents, 25% are very good, 25% are good, 17% are average, 17% are bad and 17% are very bad.

TOOLS FOR ANALYSIS

1 CHI-SQUARE

To find out the association between gender and awareness about the benefits of ESI scheme. **Null hypothesis (H0):** There is no significant difference between gender and awareness about the benefits of ESI scheme. **Alternate hypothesis (H1):** There is a significant difference between gender and awareness about the benefits of ESI scheme.

	Gender	Are you aware about the benefits under ESI schemes?
Chi-Square	.008 ^a	4.479 ^b
df	1	2
Asymp. Sig.	.928	.106
a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 60.5.		
b. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 40.3.		

INFERENCE:

The significant value is 0.05 is lesser than 0.106 ($0.05 < 0.106$). Hence H0 is accepted and H1 rejected. There is no association between gender and awareness about the benefits of ESI scheme.

2. CORRELATION

To find out the relationship between frequently utilizing the ESI benefits and ESI benefit influence employee retention engagement. **Null hypothesis (H0):** There is no relationship difference between frequently utilizing the ESI benefits and ESI benefit influence employee retention engagement. **Alternate hypothesis (H1):** There is a relationship difference between frequently utilizing the ESI benefits and ESI benefit influence employee retention engagement.

and H1 is accepted. There is relationship between frequently utilizing the ESI benefits and ESI benefit influence employee retention engagement.

SUMMARY FINDINGS

- According to the study, it is found that out of 121 respondents, 50.41% are male and 49.51% are female
- According to the study, it is found that out of 121 respondents, 33% are 21 – 30, 33% are 31 -40, 26% are 41 – 50 and 8% are above 51.
- According to the study, it is found that out of 121 respondents, 17% are SSLC, 41% are HSC, 8% are ITI / Diploma, 26% are Graduate and 8% are others.
- According to the study, it is found that out

		Do you frequently Utilize the ESI benefits provided by the ESI schemes?	Does ESI benefit influence employee retention engagement towards job?
Do you frequently utilize the ESI benefits provided by the ESI schemes?	Pearson Correlation	1	.262**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.004
	N	121	121
Does ESI benefit influence employee retention engagement towards job?	Pearson Correlation	.262**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.004	
	N	121	121

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

INFERENCE:

The significant value is 0.05 is greater than 0.004 ($0.05 > 0.004$). Hence H0 is rejected

of 121 respondents, 25% are less than 10000, 26% are 10001 – 15000, 25% are 15001 – 20000, 25% are 20001 – 25000.

- According to the study, it is found that out of 121 respondents, 33% are fully aware,

41% are partially aware and 26% are not at all aware

- According to the study, it is found that out of 121 respondents, 33% are always, 17% are often, 17% are sometimes, 17% are rarely and 17% are never.
- According to the study, it is found that out of 121 respondents, 50% are extremely unlikely, 17% are unlikely, 17% are average, 9% are likely and 8% are extremely likely.
- According to the study, it is found that out of 121 respondents, 42.15% are complex, 24.79% are simple and 33.06% are no opinion.
- According to the study, it is found that out of 121 respondents, 16.53% are distance to the esi dispensary, 33.06% are lack of medicines and other facilities, 25.82% are bottleneck procedures, 8.26% are delay in getting claims and 16.53% are misbehaviour or restrictions of supporting staff.
- According to the study, it is found that out of 121 respondents, 17% are strongly disagree, 41% are disagree, 17% are neutral, 17% are agree and 8% are strongly agree.
- According to the study, it is found that out of 121 respondents, 25% are very good, 25% are good, 17% are average, 17% are bad and 17% are very bad.

SUGGESTIONS

The organization is supposed to place the details of ESI benefits in the notice board. Employees should get the benefits even after the retirement. The company needs to focus under the benefits of Employee State Insurance (ESI) policy to the Employee of the company. The organization should give more awareness about the funeral benefits to the employees. Free medical camp should be organized by the employer. Most of the employees know about all the benefits under ESI but those who all joined new in the organization they are not aware about all benefit under ESI, so employer should give them proper knowledge about all the benefits. There must be increase in the number of ESI dispensaries. Employees have to attend seminars about the ESI benefits. The delivery of services in social security through the Employees' State Insurance Scheme (ESIS) should be improved with the help of Information Technology (IT) in order to adopt the transparency and good governance in services of the ESIC. The bottleneck procedures can be avoided. The Employee should be properly educated under the Employee State Insurance (ESI) policy.

CONCLUSION

The working environment will be healthy only when the Organization and the Employees together have a growth so that it will be Healthy Organization. Employees need to focus on Awareness and Utilization of

ESI policy more familiar. Employers have to provide proper awareness to employees on Employee State Insurance. Social Security measures have introduced an element of stability and production in the midst of distress and strain of modern life. The ESI scheme is financed by the ESI fund consisting of contributions from employers, employees, grants, donations and gifts of Central and State governments and Local authorities. The organization will be healthy only when the employee and the organizations together have a growth so that it will be healthy organization. All the employee's should aware about employee state insurance scheme (ESI) so that it will be beneficiary for their medical problems. From this study it is founded that maximum number of workers are aware and majority of the workers are utilizing the benefits of ESI services.

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